

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENCE AND ITS RESEARCH.

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Abstract The article shows the solution to the psychological problems of the younger generation associated with learning and changes in their attention, senses and imagination in early adolescence. During early adolescence, the moral relations of family and society receive information about what the realization of the personal “I” is based on active activity.

Key words: teenager, attention, stage, psychophysiological aspect of the relationship, hormonal processes, psycho-emotional, physiologist, process.

The birth of a person is one of the true miracles. The baby, who announced his birth to the whole world yesterday, will soon begin to stand on his feet. Caught up in the sweet worries of the world, parents do not even notice how their little children grow up, reach the stage of childhood and then adolescence. Our wise people have a proverb: when a child is small, his worries are small, and when a son or daughter grows up, their worries become greater.

The psychological problems of the younger generation related to education and learning have regularly attracted the attention of great scientists, philosophers and writers. The first works of pedagogical and psychological content formed the basis of religious and moral teachings of the 17th-18th centuries. Examples of psychological research in Russia were formed in various works devoted to the human psyche under the influence of Eastern and Western culture. The initial

views in the works of V.N. Tatishev, A.N. Radishchev, N.I. Novikov and others were influenced by the characteristics of mental development and differences in mental development. Abu Rayhrn Beruni's thoughts about the purpose, objectives and state of education and upbringing, human development and the younger generation are correct. n a sense, it was created on the basis of humanitarianism and the humanities. The principles of natural harmony between education and upbringing can be observed in all the works of the thinker. He emphasizes that man is part of nature. The book of the Russian historian V.N. Tatishev “Conversation about the benefits of sciences and knowledge” shows the classification of sciences, the meaning of knowledge, the position of language and speech, their connection with the characteristics of youth. Delving into the nature of outdoor education, age-appropriate learning exudes harmony with nature. In Beruni's pedagogical work, the main issues were man and his happiness, education and maturity. Abu Ali ibn Sina, a sage and genius of medicine, who lived and worked in the Middle Ages, provides valuable information about the human psyche, the unity of body and soul, the structure of the human body, the activity of the nerves in it and their branching. and their conditions still form an important basis in medicine.

From a physiological point of view, the body of our boys and girls experiencing adolescence develops extremely quickly. It is during this period that they begin to develop secondary sexual characteristics. Very living processes are taking place in their psyche, their worldview is changing. All these processes place a huge burden on the nervous system of adolescents. Boys and girls in adolescence become restless and sometimes aggressive. To this day, the fact that their child, who has previously had a difficult time, suddenly changes so much makes most parents rush. Adults don't know how to deal with their teenage children. In general, adults should be careful, attentive and tolerant towards boys and girls during adolescence. During this time, the body's production of a number

of hormones increases. For boys, the transition period begins one to two years later than for girls. . Here I would like to emphasize one thing: there are no clear boundaries of adolescence. In addition, the characteristics of this period are expressed differently in each child. Because every human body develops based on its own rhythms. According to experts, from childhood to adolescence

The transition period can last from 10-11 years to 15-17 years. Both psychologists and doctors recognize the period of transition from childhood to adolescence as a period of extremely complex psychophysiological processes. Experts teach that the transition period can be divided into three stages. The first stage is a period of preparation for complex changes that are expected psychophysiological. The second stage is a transitional period in the literal sense of the word, and at the third stage the psychophysiological changes end. During this period, the attitude of boys and girls towards each other changes, their interest increases. They take great care of their appearance. Children of the transition period face a very difficult task - they have to say goodbye to childhood and step into the world of adults. In such a situation, a person who is not a child, but also not an adult, first of all needs the help of his parents, and in addition, the help of older relatives. Adults should inform them about the characteristics of adolescence and adolescence. give them a medical brochure or booklet. During the transition from childhood to adolescence, dramatic changes can occur in the psyche of boys and girls. The world they knew in childhood suddenly changes and begins to take on a completely unfamiliar form. It is more difficult for them to perceive and accept impressions from the rapidly changing outside world. At such times, they need the help and support of adults. To do this, adults in the family of adolescents need to understand the changes of the transition period.

Changes in appearance are not the only sign of the beginning of the transition period in children entering adolescence. We have already mentioned

that important changes during this period also affect the child's psyche. Because of this, their character can change dramatically. Just yesterday, the character of a polite, attentive, polite boy suddenly changed, and at the same time he was angry, every he becomes suspicious of things, rude, easily offended, argues in vain. The entire existence of children during the transition period changes - the psychosomatic state, character, worldview. Dramatic changes in children's mental health naturally affect their health. As a matter of fact, the basis of all the problems that arise during this period are sharp psychological and physiological changes. Our children don't understand what this situation is and they get angry because of it. Imagine a situation where a person, who was enjoying a sweet childhood, suddenly plunges into the abyss of a terrible crisis, not knowing what consequences await him. The transition experience becomes a testing time for our children. Naturally, in such a situation, both the fragile hearts of our children and sensitive bodies suffer equally. Teenagers can often develop various diseases. Here I would like to emphasize one thing: transitional diseases are caused by the inability of some organs of the body to develop in accordance with rapid psychophysiological changes. These diseases can disappear on their own due to the normalization of the development of internal organs and processes in the body of a teenager. One of the problems that worries our boys and girls in adolescence is a rash that can be observed on the skin of the face. and the body due to sudden hormonal changes (offensive). In addition, in most cases, our teenagers are troubled by disorders of the autonomic blood system (dystonia), depression (mental depression), typical of the transition period.

Disorder of the autonomic blood system (dystonia) is a disruption of the autonomic nervous system, which serves to maintain internal balance in the human body. Typically, such disturbances in the functional activity of the human body occur under the influence of strong hormonal processes and psycho-

emotional stress. From a clinical point of view, such changes include very rapid heartbeat, dizziness, increased sweating, and low blood pressure.

symptoms such as vomiting, various abdominal pains, nausea, fatigue of the body, dizziness. In general, at the end of the transition period, the above clinical symptoms disappear on their own.

Early adolescence is defined as the threshold of maturity. This stage of maturity includes physiological, psychological and social boundaries. The science of psychology calls for a comprehensive study of the problem of adolescence. This is a very difficult question, since in terms of the pace of psychophysiological development its stages do not always coincide with the period of social maturation. As a result of the acceleration, the progress of our children today is two to three years ahead of previous generations. Physiologists divide this process into 3 stages depending on the appearance of secondary sexual characteristics:

Stage I – prepubertal period;

Stage II – puberty;

Stage III – post-pubertal period.

Developmental psychology previously associated adolescence with stages I-II; due to acceleration, the age limit of adolescence now ranges from 15-16 to 18 years. So, adolescence begins earlier. However, the specific content of this period of development is determined primarily by social conditions. The role of youth in society, its status, and factors depend on social conditions. Teenagers should not be considered adults. Because childhood can be observed in their personality traits. This can be seen in their thoughts, lives and future relationships. Many teenagers are irresponsible when choosing a profession, even by the time they graduate from school. This period is characterized by the moral self-awareness of the teenager, as well as the transition to a new stage of morality. Teenagers with well-developed intelligence can understand and discuss issues that concern adults.

Teenagers ponder answers to many problematic questions. They are more interested in moral issues. If teachers are the source of solutions to moral issues for primary school students, then teenagers will look more for answers to these questions among their peers. Teenagers and when searching for the correct answer to a question, they turn to sources used by older people. Such sources are predominantly real, multifaceted, complex human relationships and scientific ones - popular fiction, journalistic literature, industrial works, the press, radio, television. Today's teenagers have a cautious, intellectually practical outlook on life, freedom and independence. They are also realistic about the concept of righteousness.

are approaching. For example, as in previous years, they understand and interpret that “righteousness is not the same for everyone, but it is determined for each according to his capabilities and for each according to his work or contribution to human interests.” By the time they graduate from school, many teenagers have developed and strengthened certain moral standards.

The characteristic problems of boys gradually entering adolescence after saying goodbye to childhood are inextricably linked with a feeling of increased physical strength and the intensification of the processes of sexual growth. Boys this age want to tell the world that they have grown up. As a result, they experience psychological stress. During adolescence, the character of boys changes dramatically. Adolescents strive to behave like adults, but are constantly in a state of internal conflict because they do not have the psychophysiological abilities characteristic of adults. As a result, extreme nervousness and even aggressiveness can be seen in their character. In the psyche of children of this period, a balance of rights and responsibilities has not yet been formed. Boys, under the influence of various internal conflicts, in most cases become asocial, stubborn, very shy or, conversely, very aggressive. , helpless. During this period,

the influence of the family environment on adolescents becomes more significant. If there is mutual harmony, respect and sincerity in the family, adolescents will be able to soften their internal conflicts and change their behavior in a positive direction. If the family situation is difficult, on the contrary, the negative character characteristics of adolescents begin to take on a more dramatic form. Children become disadvantaged and exposed to the influence of the street.

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